

SO‘Z TURKUMLARI VA ULARNING XUSUSIYATLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA. Ushbu maqolada grammatikaning tarmog‘i bo‘lmish morfologiya, so‘z turkumlari va ularning sifatlari haqida so‘z yuritilgan bo‘lib, grammatik vositalarning alohida ma‘nolari ifodalangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: morfologiya, ot, fe‘l, sifat, son, olmosh, ravish, yordamchi so‘z turkumlari, taqlid so‘zlar, undov so‘zlar.

So‘zlarning lug‘aviy va grammatik ma‘no jihatdan o‘xshashligiga ko‘ra ayrim leksik grammatik munosabatga kirishadi. So‘zlarni turkumlarga ajratish ularni grammatik ma‘nolari bilan bir qatorda, lug‘aviy ma‘nosi ham asosiy belgilardan hisoblanadi. Ham grammatik ham leksik manoga ega bo‘lgan so‘z turkumlari kiradi. Gapda mustaqil sintaktik bo‘lak sifatida ishtirok etadigan so‘zlar mustaqil so‘zlar deyiladi. Mustaqil so‘zlarga: ot, sifat, son, olmosh kiradi.

Shuni ham ta‘kidlash joizki, tilimizdagi ba‘zi mustaqil so‘zlar ham nutq jarayonida o‘zini mustaqil jarayonini yo‘qotib grammatik ma‘no ifodalashga xislangan bo‘ladi. Bu hodisa tilshunoslikda grammatikalizatsiya deb yuritiladi. M: ko‘rib qolmoq, bilib qolmoq, hafta ichi kabi so‘zlarda qol, ich kabi so‘zlarda o‘zining mustaqil ma‘nosini yo‘qotgan holda yordamchi so‘zlarda qo‘llanadi.

Mustaqil leksik manoga ega bo‘lmaydigan gap bo‘lagi vazifasini bajara olmaydigan biroq so‘z va gaplarni o‘zaro bog‘lash yoki ularga qo‘shimcha mano nozikligi kiritish uchun xizmat qiladigan so‘zlar jumlasiga kiradi.

Yordamchi so‘zlar umumiy vazifalarga ko‘ra uch guruhga bo‘linadi.

1) ko‘makchi, 2) bog‘lovchi, 3) yuklama

Bevosita ot o‘rnida qo‘llanuvchi. Xususan ism guruhiga mansub M: Men, hech kim, hech nima o‘z olmoshlari har doim birgalikda ishlatiladi.

Fe‘lning harakat nomi shakllari ham xususan birlikda ishlatiladigan so‘zlardandir. Olmoshning boshqa turlari birlik va ko‘plikda ishlatilishi mumkin. M: sen, senlar u - ular, siz - sizlar, kim - kimlar kabi. Bu olmoshlardan ba‘zilari lar affiksi qo‘shilganda ular turli mano nozikliklarini

anglatadi. Ism guruhiga mansub sifat, sifat o'rnida ishlatiladigan olmoshlar va bazi ravishlar va felning sifatdosh shakli kabi so'zlarga lar qo'shimchasi otlashish asosi grammatik son tushunchasi yuzaga keladi.

M: yaxshilar, kattalar kabi bir qancha misollar bilan keltirsak bo'ladi .

Miqdor sonlarga -lar qo'shimchasi qo'shilganda taxmin, chama ma'nosi qo'llanadi.

M: Soat ikkilarda uchrashamiz.

Ko'plik affiksi fe'llarda ham ko'p qo'llanadi. So'z turkumlari doirasida juda ham yorqin tarzda qo'shimchalar qo'llanadi. Ko'plik affiksi fe'llarda qo'langanda birlik ma'nosi tushuniladi. M: bordilar - borishdi.

Muayyan narsaning uch shaxsdan biriga taniqli ekanini anglatuvchi umumiy manolar va ularning lug'aviy ma'nosini bildiruvchi so'zlarga aytiladi

Egalik affiksatsiyasi unli bilan so'z va so'z turkumlari shakillariga qo'shib kelishi mumkin.

Demak, egalik affiksatsiyasida angkashilgan birlik va ko'plik tushunchasi narsaga emas balki so'zlovchi, tinglovchi o'zga kabi grammatik shaxslarga dahldor.

Egalik affiksi grammatik ma'no bilan birga son ma'nosini ham ifodalaydi.

M: Kitob - kitobi, Kitob - kitobing, Kitob - kitoblari

Egalik affiksatsiya ot va otdan boshqa so'zlar bilan qo'langanda quyidagi xususiyatlarga ega.

1) O'zakka egalik qo'shimchalari qo'shish bilan tovush ortishi.

2)Egalik affiksatsiyasi 1va 2 shaxda birgalik ma'nosida kelishi.

3) Egalik qo'shimchalari otdan boshqa qo'shimchalarga qo'shib keladi.

4) Egalik qo'shimchalari o'zi qo'shilgan sana bilan birga boshqa qo'shimchalar bilan bog'lanib keladi.

Egalik kategoryalariga xos 1-, 2-shaxs affiksi so'z yasovchi va so'z o'zgartirivchi bazi qo'shimchalar bilan shakldoshlik hosil qiladi.

a) egalik va ot yasovchi qo'shimcha M: Bola + M bolam

b) birinchi shaxs birlik M: ota+ otam, aka+ akam

Egalik yoki niki affik 2 shaxs birligi va qaratqich kelishigi men, sen olmoshlariga qo'shilganida mening sening

Biroq bunday holda egalik affikslari o'zi qo'shilib kelgan otga almashiniladi.

Otning boshqa so'zlar bilan sintaktik munosabatini ko'rsatuvchi manolar va shu ma'noni ifodalovchi shaklar tizimi kelishik kategoriyasi deb yuritiladi.

Otning kelishik kategoriyasini olib o'zgarishi tuslanish deyiladi. Kelishik affikslari esa turlanish deyiladi

Turlovchilar affiksial morfemalarning so'z o'zgartiruvchi qo'shimchasiga kiradi. So'z o'zgartiruvchi (sintaktik shakl yasovchi) sirasiga mansub .

O'zbek tilida oltita kelishik mavjud bo'lib ularning turlari alohida vazifa bajarib keladi.

Makon zamon kelishiklar ham bazan o'rin payt kelishiklarida qo'llanib kelaoladi. O'rin va chiqish kelishiklari ham bazan boshqa so'zlar bilan qo'shilib kela oladi. M: Otdan baland, itdan past, uyat o'limdan qattiq, xalqimga aziz.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik”, “og’ir dard”, “yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>

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²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

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²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

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